

ON THE NATURE OF LEAD-ACETATO COMPLEX ION AND THE LEAD ACETATE MOLECULE

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The formation of the cationic complex $PbAc^+$ ion has been studied by measurements of the lowering of freezing point of the system eutectic $KNO_3 \cdot H_2O$, by mixtures of $Pb(NO_3)_2$ and KAc solutions.

By the same method it has been shown that the complex $PbAc^+$ and Ac^- ions are produced by the primary dissociation of lead acetate molecule in solution.

The formation of a lead-acetato complex ion by the reaction between a lead salt and an alkali or ammonium acetate in solution has been established through the work of Edmonds and Birnbown (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 2367) and Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (this *Journal*, 1946, **23**, 39), the former workers employing solubility measurements and the latter, from thermometric and conductometric titrations.

Although the methods of study applied by Purkayastha and Sen Sarma appear more accurate than their foregoing workers, the Job's method of continued variation employed by them to obtain the value of the instability constant of the complex ion is subject to criticism in the present case.

A constant value for instability constant can also be obtained if a two-fold condensed ion $[Pb_2Ac_2]^{++}$ is assumed in place of a single ion $[PbAc]^+$ as advocated by previous workers.

Such an assumption is supported by the fact that one of the lead-acetato perchlorates, isolated by Weinland and Stroch (*Ber.* 1922, **85**, 553, 2706) has been formulated as a two-fold condensed complex $[Pb_2Ac_2][ClO_4]_2 \cdot H_2O$ from the measurement of its conductivity in solution.

Besides, a large number of inorganic molecules, formerly regarded as simple molecules, have been shown by physico-chemical measurements during recent years to exist in polymerised state in solution.

From these considerations it appears that in the absence of some direct evidence, the nature of the lead-acetato complex ion is still unsettled and calculation of its dissociation constant by the foregoing workers is based on a somewhat arbitrary assumption that a simple $[PbAc]^+$ ion is formed.

The present author has followed the reaction between lead nitrate and potassium acetate in solution from measurements of the depression of freezing points of the eutectic $KNO_3 \cdot H_2O$ (2.87°). The method is based on the observation of Lowenharz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1895, **16**, 70) that the cryoscopic rule of Raoult is applicable to the case of (1) transition point of a salt hydrate, (2) melting point of the salt hydrate and (3) the eutectics, and was first employed by Darmonis (*Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1927, **36**, 64) and later by Cornec and Muller (*Compt. rend.*, 1932, **194**, 1735), and particularly by Souchey (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1946, *v*, **13**, 160) during recent years for determining the state of aggregation of a large number of inorganic ions in solution.

The lowering of freezing point is connected with the concentration of the dissolved solute by the simple equation $\Delta t = K.C$, where Δt = lowering of freezing point, C = concentration in g. moles of the dissolved substance or ion and K = molecular lowering constant = 1.7 for a single ion or an undissociated molecule.

The present method of study has been employed because of its having the following advantages over the classical cryoscopic method :

(1) The value of the molecular lowering changes very slightly with changes of concentration C of the dissolved substance, as the ionic force of the medium is primarily due to the ions of the salt hydrate and the addition of small quantities of the substance, molecular lowering of which is to be measured, changes the ionic force very little.

(2) The lowering of freezing point of the eutectic $\text{KNO}_3 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is independent of the presence of K^+ and NO_3^- ions liberated by the dissolved potassium acetate and lead nitrate, and only the complex ion formed and its dissociation products will exert any influence in depressing the freezing point of the eutectic.

Freezing point measurements in the above system by mixing together lead nitrate and potassium acetate in different proportions indicate that a complex lead acetate ion is formed by interaction between these substances, in which the lead and acetate ions are in the ratio 1:1.

Comparison of the theoretical values of depression of the freezing point calculated from the values of the instability constant K of the $[\text{PbAc}]^+$ ion obtained by the foregoing workers and from the value of K , calculated by the author on the assumption of a two-fold condensed ion $[\text{Pb}_2\text{Ac}_2]^{++}$, have been made with the experimental value.

It has been found that the experimental value of the lowering closely agrees with the theoretical value calculated from the value of K obtained by Edmonds and Birnbow and is somewhat smaller than that calculated from the data of Purkayastha and Sen Sarma. The result shows that the complex ion is PbAc^+ ion, as has been assumed by the foregoing workers.

The low value of the degree of dissociation of the lead acetate molecule, obtained from conductivity measurements, was explained by Sandved (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1967), that the $[\text{PbAc}]^+$ ion is probably formed by primary dissociation of the lead acetate molecule.

The present author has adduced direct evidence in this respect from measurement of the lowering of freezing point of the system eutectic $\text{KNO}_3 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ by lead acetate. It has been found that at different concentrations of lead acetate, the depression corresponds to the formation of two ions only in solution, from dissociation of the lead acetate molecule.

The simplest way of interpreting these results is to assume that the lead acetate behaves in solution mainly as a binary electrolyte dissociating into PbAc^+ and Ac^- ions in solution according to the equation,

the secondary dissociation of the lead-acetato ion formed is practically so negligible that the lead acetate molecule may be looked upon as a complex acetato-acetate of lead.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Merck's lead nitrate, potassium nitrate, potassium acetate and lead acetate of analytical reagent quality have been used in all the measurements.

The freezing point measurements were carried out in the Beckmann's apparatus commonly used in the laboratories. The cooling bath was provided by a mixture of crushed ice and common salt, the temperature at equilibrium not falling below 10° .

In Table I and Fig. 1 have been shown the experimental data of freezing point measurements of mixtures of solutions of lead nitrate and potassium acetate in 1.2 M-KNO₃.

The break in the curve (Fig. 1) indicates the proportion in which the complex formation takes place.

Results of freezing point measurements of solutions containing mixtures of potassium acetate and lead nitrate in equimolecular proportions in 1.2 molar KNO₃ have been shown in Table II. Curve in Fig. 2 has been drawn to indicate the constancy of the value of $\Delta t/C$ at different concentrations.

Table III and the accompanying curve in Fig. 3 show the data for freezing point measurements of pure lead acetate solutions in different concentrations in 1.2 M-KNO₃ solutions.

TABLE I

Freezing point measurements of mixtures of 0.2 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO₃ and 0.4 M-Pb(NO₃)₂ in 1.2 M-KNO₃ made up to 50 c.c. with 1.2 M-KNO₃.

0.2 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ employed.	0.4 M-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ employed.	1.2 M-KNO ₃ added.	F.P. of the mixture. (Beckmann).	Lowering of F.P. of the eutectic KNO ₃ -H ₂ O (Δt).
0 c.c.	0 c.c.	50 c.c.	1.500°	
25	0	25	1.670°	0.170°
25	2.5	22.5	1.680°	0.180°
25	5	20	1.685°	0.185°
25	7.5	17.5	1.700°	0.200°
25	10	15	1.710°	0.210°
25	12.5	12.5	1.725°	0.225°
25	15	10	1.750°	0.250°
25	17.5	7.5	1.775°	0.275°
25	20	5	1.805°	0.305°
25	22.5	2.5	1.835°	0.335°
25	25	0	1.865°	0.365°

TABLE II

Freezing point measurements of mixtures of equimolecular solutions of Pb(NO₃)₂ and KAc in 1.2 M-KNO₃ in constant vol. of 50 c.c.

Solutions employed.	F. P. registered (Beckmann).	Lowering of F. P. (Beckmann).	Δt/°C.
50 c.c. of 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.500°		
25 c.c. of 0.2 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ +25 c.c. of 0.2 M-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ .	1.725°	0.225°	2.25
25 c.c. of 0.1 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ +25 c.c. of 0.1 M-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ .	1.605°	0.105°	2.15
25 c.c. of 0.6666 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ +25 c.c. of 0.6666 M-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ .	1.575°	0.075°	2.25
25 c.c. of 0.04 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ +25 c.c. of 0.04 M-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ .	1.545°	0.045°	2.25
25 c.c. of 0.15 M-KAc in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ +25 c.c. of 0.15 M-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃ .	1.665°	0.165°	2.20

TABLE III

Freezing point measurements of lead acetate in diff. conc. in 1.2M-KNO₃.

Solutions employed.	F. P. (Beckmann).	Lowering of F. P.	$\Delta t/C$.
50 c.c. of 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.500°		
50 c.c. of 0.1 M-Pb(Ac) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.840°	0.340°	3.4
50 c.c. of 0.075 M-Pb(Ac) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.455°	0.255°	3.4
50 c.c. of 0.05 M-Pb(Ac) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.670°	0.170°	3.4
50 c.c. of 0.0333 M-Pb(Ac) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.615°	0.115°	3.45
50 c.c. of 0.025 M-Pb(Ac) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.585°	0.085°	3.4
50 c.c. of 0.02 M-Pb(Ac) ₂ in 1.2 M-KNO ₃	1.565°	0.065°	3.25

Assuming that the complex ion formed is Pb₂Ac₃⁺⁺ from the reaction
 $2Pb^{++} + 2Ac^{-} = Pb_2Ac_3^{++}$

we can get the value of the dissociation constant of this ion from the general equation of Job modified into the following form:

$$K = \frac{2C^2 p [x(p+x)-1]^4}{(p-1)^3 (1-2x)} \quad \dots (1)$$

where C = molar conc. of Pb⁺⁺ ion in solution, p = molar conc. of Ac⁻ ion in soln and x c.c. of Ac⁻ combining with $1-x$ of Pb⁺⁺ produces the maximum changing effect.

Employing the data for the maximum change of conductivity given by Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (in Table VIII, *loc. cit.*) it has been found that a constant value for K in the above expression (1) can be had at different concentrations of the components, the average value being equal to 43.67×10^{-6} .

In the following table has been shown the theoretical value of the molecular lowering of freezing point of the system eutectic KNO₃-H₂O by the lead-acetato complex ion [PbAc]⁺ from the values of the degree of dissociation of the ion, calculated from the values of the dissociation constant K of the complex ion given by foregoing workers. The value of the molecular lowering of the freezing point, assuming the formation of the two-fold complex ion PbAc₂⁺⁺, has also been calculated and incorporated in the table.

TABLE IV

Authors.	K .	α .	Mol. lowering of F.P.
Edmonds and Birnbow			
PbAc ⁺ = Pb ⁺⁺ + Ac ⁻	9.65×10^{-3} at 25°	0.3636	2.328°
Purkayastha and Sen Sarma			
PbAc ⁺ = Pb ⁺⁺ + Ac ⁻	40.76×10^{-3} at 30°	0.4662	2.492°
Pb ₂ Ac ₃ ⁺⁺ = 2Pb ⁺⁺ + 2Ac ⁻	43.76×10^{-6} at 30°	0.3450	3.5°

DISCUSSION

It will appear from the data in Tables I and II and Figs. 1 and 2 that the values of the lowering of the freezing point of the system eutectic $\text{KNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ by solution molar with respect to both Pb^{++} and acetate ions is 2.25° . Assuming that such a solution contains the two-fold ion $[\text{Pb}_2\text{Ac}_2]^{++}$ and its products of dissociation Pb^{++} and Ac^- ions, the total depression of freezing point of the system eutectic $\text{KNN}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ from the value of the degree of dissociation calculated in Table IV of the complex ion $[\text{Pb}_2\text{Ac}_2]^{++}$ is found out to be equal to 1.75° . This value is much smaller than the experimental value 2.25° . The two-fold polymerised ion $[\text{Pb}_2\text{Ac}_2]^{++}$ does not therefore exist.

The experimental value of the molecular depression of freezing point, however, agrees nearly with the value of depression calculated from Edmond and Birnbrown's data and somewhat lower than that of Purkayastha and Sen Sarma (cf. Table IV).

However, the formation of the ion $[\text{PbAc}]^+$ is certain as would appear both from the above calculations and the actual method of study employed by the present author.

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